

Multi-objective optimization of blended cement mortars from copper slags

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Graphical abstract

Abstract

While researchers are on the lookout for replacing traditional Portland cement in concrete mix designs, typical Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs) like fly ash and ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS) are expected to soon phase out. For any new SCM, it is necessary to have a holistic perspective based on performance, cost and CO₂ equivalent in order to judge their efficacy in a binder system. In this study, the potential of copper slag as an SCM in a ternary blended system has been explored using a multi-objective optimization framework where regression models predicting compressive strength were developed and solved inversely with cost and CO₂ equivalent linear models. Optimization of blended cement mix designs of two different strength classes (42.5N and 32.5N) were demonstrated in this paper. The primary goal of this paper was to develop an experimental and statistical modelling framework which can be used to generate possible mix designs pertaining to specific cement strength classes with minimal cost and CO₂ equivalent. A cement strength class of 42.5N was obtained with approximately 40 wt% replacement of Portland cement by copper slag and limestone. The aforementioned framework based on experimental design, linear regression and MOLP can be useful for both copper and cement industries in terms of limiting the number of experimental trials and generating new target-based mix designs from previously obtained data.

1. Introduction

It is commonly known that cement production accounts for approximately 8% global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions amounting to approximately 2.8 Gt/year (Ellis et al. 2020). Hence, at the turn of this millennium, research activities related to cement replacement and

32 alternative cements gained ground. Different materials like fly ash, ground granulated blast
33 furnace slag (GGBFS), silica fume, etc. have been used as a Supplementary Cementitious
34 Material (SCM) in order to reduce the effective usage of cement clinker in concrete systems
35 (Scrivener et al. 2018). However, due to the prominence of alternative energy sources, the
36 production of fly ash from thermal power plants is expected to plummet (International
37 Energy Agency 2009). Additionally, modern processes may deem the fly ash unsuitable for
38 use in concrete systems (International Energy Agency 2009). While the unavailability of fly
39 ash and GGBFS can be concerning, it provides an opportunity to tap into the market of
40 unconventional SCMs like copper slags (Mahajan and Muhammad 2024; Stefanini et al. 2023
41), bauxite residue (Di Mare and Ouellet-Plamondon 2023; Pratap et al. 2024) and calcined
42 clays (K. Scrivener et al. 2018).

43 Copper slags are typically primary/secondary residues from the copper industry with a high
44 iron content. As SCMs, copper slags have been blended with Portland cement, limestone and
45 gypsum (Hallet et al. 2023). Hallet et al. (2022) used a combination of Portland cement and
46 copper slag where 30 % replacement of Portland cement corresponded to a strength class of
47 52.5N as per EN standards. An important observation for such blended systems was a
48 reduction in compressive strength at an early age but enhancement of the same after 28 days
49 (Hallet et al. 2022). Hallet et al., 2020 also reported a reduction in reactivity of copper slags
50 at early ages but similar in reactivity to fly ash at later ages. In addition to blended cement
51 systems, alkali-activated systems have been developed using copper slags as a precursor
52 (Beersaerts et al. 2021; Xu et al. 2024). Ascensão et al. (2019) used engineered slags
53 representing non-ferrous metallurgical slags to develop inorganic polymer mortars using a
54 potassium silicate activator. Compressive strength in the range of 20-30 MPa was obtained
55 for specimens cured at ambient temperatures. However, specimens cured at 60 °C exhibited
56 compressive strengths up to 100 MPa. Recently, hybrid binders were developed from copper
57 slags, by combining some of the benefits of blended cement systems and alkali activated
58 systems (Arnout et al. 2021). Hybrid binders incorporate a higher amount of SCM than
59 blended cement systems, which consequently reduces the Portland cement usage.

60 Additionally, in place of activators like potassium silicate that typically entail a high carbon
61 footprint, sodium or potassium hydroxide (Arnout et al. 2021) and sodium or potassium salts
62 (Cristelo et al. 2021) have been used as alkali activators. Arnout et al. (2021) used 70 %
63 copper slag and 10 % Portland cement (remaining 10 % includes additives like gypsum and
64 limestone) with 0.9 M NaOH solution to develop mortar mixes satisfying the requirements
65 for 52.5N strength class. The creation of these low carbon binder systems are as per the new
66 roadmap published by Cembureau (Cembureau, 2020). A target CO₂ equivalent of 550
67 kg_{CO2}/ton of cement has been set for the year 2050 whereas the equivalent CO₂ for 2017 was
68 667 kg_{CO2}/ton. In this study, we focus on blended cement systems with copper slags due to
69 their abundance (Sivakumar 2021) and the possibility to reduce the CO₂ equivalent of
70 cementitious binders using mathematical techniques. It is also to be noted that majority of the
71 studies cited above used performance-based methods or one-factor-at-a-time (OFAT) method
72 to develop optimal mix designs. The following paragraph focuses on experimental design
73 techniques which are better than OFAT techniques in terms of parameter interactions.

74 Experimental design techniques have often been applied in the field of concrete materials in
75 order to reduce the number of experiments for a specific target and also to have statistical
76 significance for the results obtained. Meng et al. (2018) and Maaze and Shrivastava (2023)

77 used a full factorial experimental design to evaluate the effects of mixture parameters on the
78 properties of Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC) and brick-waste geopolymers
79 respectively. While a full factorial design is the best possible design in terms of statistical
80 inference, the number of experiments increases exponentially with the addition of a new
81 factor. A fractional-factorial design can be used to solve this problem where the number of
82 experiments is reduced without significantly altering the amount of information generated
83 from the experimental design. Lopez-Gayarre et al. (2011) used a fractional factorial design
84 to assess the properties of recycled concrete using 7 factors and only 27 experimental runs.
85 Other classical designs employed in the field of concrete materials include central composite
86 design (Wan Hassan et al. 2020), Box-Behnken design (Maaze and Shrivastava, 2023) and
87 others. It is to be noted that the experimental designs discussed so far can both be used as
88 screening designs or at a later stage of experiments. However, it can be advantageous to
89 further reduce the number of experiments at the screening stage where the domain space of
90 experimentation is still unclear. In order to tackle this problem, Jones and Nachtsheim (2011)
91 developed a special class of minimally-aliased experimental designs called Definitive
92 Screening Designs (DSD). This design has found applications in the optimization of biodiesel
93 production parameters (Hundie and Akuma 2022), adsorption optimization of fly ash (Cave
94 and Fatehi 2018) and optimization of carbon synthesis (Libbrecht et al. 2015) . However, as
95 far as the knowledge of the authors extends, these designs have never been used in the field
96 of concrete or building materials. Data collection using suitable experimental design
97 techniques can propel better performance of Machine Learning (ML) models, some of which
98 are discussed in the following paragraph.

99 Appropriate ML algorithms are necessary to develop explainable and/or predictive models. In
100 the field of concrete and building materials, various ML models like linear regression
101 (Sobhani et al. 2010; Tam 2022), random forest (Han et al. 2019; Zhang et al. 2019), Support
102 Vector Machines (Azimi-Pour et al. 2020; Cemiloglu et al. 2023), Artificial Neural
103 Networks (Alshihri et al. 2009; Nazari and Pacheco Torgal 2013) and others have been
104 employed in order to develop models predicting certain response variables from a given set of
105 independent variables. However, as pointed out by Li et al. (Li et al. 2022), there are a
106 number of factors that need to be considered when applying such models in the field of
107 concrete science. The two most significant challenges in the application of ML models to
108 data in the field of concrete science stem from the scarcity of data itself and problems with a
109 large number of independent variables (Li et al. 2022). Hence, one of the typically
110 recommended measures involve the use of simple regression models for a start and
111 proceeding to more complex algorithms with increasing user requirements and the generation
112 of sufficient data points (Li et al. 2022). Experimental model validation also plays a key role
113 in determining the efficacy of the ML models in concrete science. In this paper, only linear
114 regression models have been considered considering the number of data points available and
115 also the final goal of the problem which is to develop a multi-objective optimization
116 framework for blended cement systems. Some optimization algorithms specifically used in
117 the field of building materials have been discussed in the following paragraph.

118 Optimization in the field of concrete materials typically refers to an objective (e.g.,
119 compressive strength) which is a function of the mix design components and/or process
120 parameters like curing type, mixing speed, etc. Some constraints can also be added depending
121 on the nature of the problem in question. While optimization can involve multiple objectives,

122 single objective optimization problems (Cheng et al. 2014; Meng et al. 2017) have mostly
123 been in focus in the field of building materials. However, recently, due to the need of holistic
124 assessment of building materials, research on multi-objective optimization has gained ground.
125 Irrespective of the number of objectives, linear programs (Roshavelov 2005), non-linear
126 programs (Muthukumar and Mohan 2004; Şimşek et al. 2014) and metaheuristic optimization
127 methods (Bouzoubaâ and Fournier 2003; Kim et al. 2013) have often been used. While linear
128 programs can easily be solved using computationally simple algorithms like the simplex
129 method (Dantzig 1990), non-linear programs can involve complexities especially when the
130 problems are not convex. When functional approximation is not feasible, metaheuristic
131 optimization techniques (Dasgupta et al. 1995) can be used to solve such problems.
132 Bouzoubaâ and Fournier (2003) used metaheuristic techniques to find the optimal fly ash
133 content in concrete while Kim et al. (2013) also used the same techniques to minimize cost
134 and CO₂ emissions in concrete. It is to be noted that both these examples were multi-
135 objective problems. Some more recent work on multi-objective optimization explored the
136 possibilities of combining objective functions to form a single objective (Bharadwaj et al.
137 2024), use of desirability functions (Heidari et al. 2024), use of Borg algorithm which is an
138 evolutionary search technique (DeRousseau et al. 2021) and the use of Gaussian models
139 (Pfeiffer et al. 2024).

140 While there has been significant progress in the use of data-centric approaches to solve
141 problems in the field of concrete science, there is still no framework that guides the user
142 through experimental designs, ML algorithms, optimization algorithms, etc. to generate
143 optimal concrete/mortar mix designs. Also, most data-centric papers employ black box ML
144 models, which limits their explainability. In the absence of extensive datasets for copper slag-
145 based blended cements, this paper exploits novel experimental design techniques to generate
146 near-uniform data in the design space and use explainable regression models and
147 scalarization techniques to solve strength-cost-CO₂ equivalent optimization problems
148 pertaining to strength classes 42.5N and 32.5N.

149

150 **2. Materials and Methods**

151

152 *2.1 Characterization of materials*

153 In this study an Fe-rich copper slag from Aurubis, Hamburg was used which is a by-product
154 from primary copper production. Portland cement (CEM I 52.5 N and CEM I 52.5 R) from
155 Holcim and limestone from Carmeuse (Calcitec 2001M) were also used to make the ternary
156 blended cement mixes. The oxide compositions of the raw materials were derived from X-ray
157 fluorescence (XRF) using a S8 Tiger (Bruker). The mineralogy of the raw materials was
158 determined by Quantitative X-ray diffraction (QXRD) using the D2 phaser (Bruker), with an
159 external TiO₂ (Kronos 2300) standard which was calibrated against a certified alumina
160 standard (NIST SRM 676a α -Al₂O₃). The X-ray diffraction measurements were conducted in
161 reflection method ($2\theta = 5^\circ - 65^\circ$), with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda=1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) at 30 kV and 10 mA.
162 Using TOPAS software and codes developed in JEdit, quantification of the phases was
163 performed using the G-factor method (Jansen et al. 2011). All characterization experiments
164 were conducted at KU Leuven.

165 The copper slag was milled to two different levels of fineness in order to study the effect of
 166 the specific surface of the copper slags on blended cement mortar systems. First, the copper
 167 slag was milled using a Fritsch Pulverisette disc mill, which was followed by milling in an
 168 attritor mill. The fineness was measured using the Blaine method (EN 196-6, 2018), while
 169 particle size distribution (PSD) was determined using the Beckman Coulter Laser Particle
 170 Size Analyzer.

171 *2.2 Design of experiments*

172 A three-stage experimental design was conducted based on the variables shown in Table 1 to
 173 generate 51 mix designs. The experimental design scheme consisted of a DSD, followed by
 174 an augmented DSD and then a space-filling Fast Flexible Filling Design (FFFD). This
 175 ensured a near uniform distribution of points in the design space as shown in Fig. 1. Principal
 176 Component Analysis (PCA) with two components was used to visualize the distribution of
 177 the points in the design space since it is copious to visualize a system with five independent
 178 variables as shown in Table 1. It is to be noted that prior to performing PCA, the independent
 179 variables were scaled and the categorical variables were binary encoded.

180
 181 The variables in Table 1 were selected based on previous research for blended cement
 182 systems containing copper slags (Hallet et al. 2020) and also pertaining to the standard for
 183 different cement classes (EN 197-1, 2011). A water-to-binder ratio lower than 0.50 was used
 184 since the use of copper slags (a denser material than Portland cement) could increase the
 185 workability. The limestone content of these binder systems corresponds to the Portland
 186 limestone-cements, which would classify as CEM II/A-L and CEM II/B-L (EN 197-1, 2011).
 187 Limestone was added in order to reduce the retarding effect of copper slag at early ages
 188 (Hallet et al. 2023). Additionally, it is known that the addition of sulphates to blended cement
 189 systems influences the formation of ettringite at an early age, which further influence early-
 190 age compressive strength (Sun et al. 2020). However, in the blended cement system discussed
 191 in this paper, no sulphates were used in order to reduce the complexity of the system for
 192 mathematical modelling.

193
 194 **Table 1:** Summary of independent variables used in the DSD

Factor	Type of variable	Level 1	Level 2
Copper slag	Continuous	20 wt % of total binder	40 wt % of total binder
Limestone-cement ratio	Continuous	0.15	0.55
Water-binder (wb) ratio	Continuous	0.45	0.50
Cement type	Discrete/Categorical	CEM I 52.5 N	CEM I 52.5 R
Copper slag fineness	Discrete/Categorical	2700 cm ² /g	4400 cm ² /g

195

Fig. 1: PCA visualization of the experimental design

All the mortar mixes were made as per the experimental design scheme discussed above and compressive strength tested as per procedures outlined in the standard (EN 196-1, 2016). Additionally, flow diameter (EN 1015-3, 1999) was measured for each mix and the cost and CO₂ equivalent were calculated based on material information in Table 2. It is to be noted that the cost and CO₂ equivalent of the mix designs are assumed to be only linear functions of the materials used in the mix design except water. Since the processes used to generate the mortar samples were identical for all the mix designs, they are not differentiating factors in terms of cost and CO₂ equivalent. Therefore, to preserve simplicity, the cost and CO₂ equivalent of mix designs were calculated based on materials' data only (Table 2). For the costs associated with the copper slags with different specific surface values, the calculations were based on assumed milling energy (refer to Appendix B) and the unit cost of electricity in Belgium which was 0.435 Euros/kWh (*Belgium - Household Electricity Prices 2024*, n.d.)

Table 2: Cost and CO₂ equivalent of material data used in this study as obtained from suppliers' information and GaBI software and EcoInvent database (refer to Appendix B) respectively.

Material	Cost (Euro/ton)	Equivalent CO ₂ (kg CO ₂ /ton)
CEM I 52.5N	140	693
CEM I 52.5R	147	817
Copper slag (2700 cm ² /g fineness)	63	70
Copper slag (4400 cm ² /g fineness)	72	73
Limestone powder	41	21

2.3 Regression models for compressive strength

221 Owing to the availability of limited data points, only linear regression models have been
222 considered in this paper. Similar regression models have been used in the field of building
223 materials with 45 samples for 4 independent variables (Chithra et al. 2016), 138 samples for
224 10 independent variables (Sözen and Yıldız 2023), 76 samples for 10 independent variables
225 (Şahin et al. 2024), etc. Additionally, data-hungry models like Artificial Neural Networks in
226 the field of building materials used 3252 samples for 11 independent variables (Wu et al.
227 2024), 153 samples for 9 independent variables (Akbarpoor et al. 2024), 260 samples for 10
228 independent variables (Oyebisi and Alomayri 2023). The following benefits were explicitly
229 targeted at when selecting linear models for regression and linear programming for solving
230 the optimization problem:

- 231
- 232 • Linear models, unlike data-hungry models like ANN need less data for effective
233 training. Often, linear models are deemed sufficient for predicting properties like
234 compressive strength in the field of building materials (Ouzia and Ben Haha 2024) .
- 235 • Linear models are explainable, that is, using t-tests, expected coefficient values, etc.,
236 the importance levels of different factors (independent variables) can be justified.
- 237 • Linear programming (LP) is a well-established method of optimization (Dantzig
238 1990). It is possible to use robust optimization techniques in conjunction with linear
239 programming which can quantify the effects of parameter uncertainty on optimization
240 performance.
- 241 • In case of non-linear problems, an easy transition from LP to quadratic programs (QP)
242 can be made, taking into account the convexity of the problem.

243

244 This stage of the work was conducted with the help of Python using the packages: scipy,
245 numpy, pandas, matplotlib, statsmodel and scikit learn. The regression models were
246 developed using normalized data of the response variables in order to use them for creating a
247 combined objective function in the case of MOLP. Eq. 1 shows the formula used for
248 normalizing the response variables.

$$249$$
$$250 \text{Norm.}(x) = \frac{x - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)} \quad (1)$$

251

252 where, Norm. (x) is the normalized form of variable x, min (x) is the minimum value of x
253 while max (x) is the maximum value of x.

254

255 The study utilized 51 mortar mix designs with corresponding compressive strength
256 measurements. The dataset was randomly partitioned into training (70%) and testing (30%)
257 sets using a fixed seed to ensure reproducibility. The analysis considered five key variables:
258 three continuous variables (copper slag percentage, limestone content percentage, and water-
259 to-binder ratio) and two categorical variables (slag fineness and cement type). Notably,
260 cement content was excluded as an independent variable due to its linear dependence on slag
261 and limestone content, which would have introduced multicollinearity issues.

262 The quality of the model fits on both training and testing data were first checked based on
263 three error metrics: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and
264 Coefficient of Determination (R²). Additionally, 5-fold cross validation was performed in
265 order to gauge the performance of the model over the entire dataset where the training and
266 testing data sets were repeatedly changed in order to check for homogeneity and possibly rule
267 out overfitting.

268

269 2.4 Multi-objective Linear Programming (MOLP)

270 2.4.1 Setting up the problem

271 The optimization problem incorporated objective functions defined in Equations 2, 3, and 4.
272 To manage the complexity introduced by categorical variables (slag fineness and cement
273 type, each with two levels), the linear programming problem was solved separately for each
274 of the four possible combinations. This approach effectively transformed a mixed-integer
275 problem into a simpler linear programming formulation, yielding four distinct solutions per
276 case.

277 The optimization considered:

- 278 • 28-day compressive strength as a function of copper slag, limestone, and water-to-
279 binder ratio
- 280 • Cost and CO₂ footprint as functions of copper slag, limestone, and cement content
- 281 • Normalized response variables for effective scalarization into a single objective
282 function.

$$283 \quad 28 \text{ day comp. strength} = A1 * \text{Copper slag}(\%) + B1 * \text{Limestone}(\%) + C1 * \text{wb ratio} \quad (2)$$

284

$$285 \quad \text{Cost} = A2 * \text{Copper slag}(\%) + B2 * \text{Limestone}(\%) + C2 * \text{Cement}(\%) \quad (3)$$

$$286 \quad \text{CO}_2 \text{ equivalent} = A3 * \text{Copper slag}(\%) + B3 * \text{Limestone}(\%) + C3 * \text{Cement}(\%) \quad (4)$$

287 where, A1, A2, A3, B1, B2, B3, C1, C2, C3 are the coefficients of the three linear equations
288 where the response variables are functions of copper slag (wt%), limestone (wt%), wb ratio
289 (water-to-binder ratio) and cement content (wt%). Eq. 2 is a regression model while
290 equations 3 and 4 are simple linear models where A2, B2 and C2 are unit costs of copper
291 slag, limestone and cement and A3, B3 and C3 are unit CO₂ equivalent values for copper
292 slag, limestone and cement.

293 In this part of the problem, normalized 28-day compressive strength, cost and CO₂ equivalent
294 have been scalarized to form a single objective function which is given by eq. 5.

295

$$296 \quad \text{Objective function} = A * 28 \text{ day comp. strength} - B * \text{Cost} - (1 - A - B) * \text{CO}_2 \text{ equivalent} \quad (5)$$

297

298

299 where, A and B are importance factors for the corresponding response variables and 28-day
300 compressive strength, cost and CO₂ equivalent are linear functions of independent variables
301 like copper slag content, cement content, limestone content, water/binder ratio, cement type
302 and fineness of slag.

303

304 2.4.2 Constraints

305

306 The constraints in this optimization problem have been defined as follows:

307

308 1. Bound constraints

309

310 The bound constraints are typically based on Table 1 since it is not possible to
311 extrapolate results beyond the domain of experimentation.

312

313 2. Equality constraint

314

315 In this problem, copper slag, cement and limestone constituted the total binder
316 content. Hence, weight percentage of all these materials need to add up to 100%. Eq.
317 6 shows the mathematical representation of the equality constraint.

318

$$319 \text{Copper slag (\%)} + \text{Limestone (\%)} + \text{Cement (\%)} = 100 \quad (6)$$

320

321 3. User-defined inequality constraints

322

323 Since the goal of the problem is to develop an inverse design scheme, constraints on
324 2-day compressive strength, 28-day compressive strength, cost and CO₂ equivalent
325 defined by the user would generate mix designs specified for the targets. For this
326 paper, the user-defined values for the two cases are mentioned in section 2.5.1.
327 Mathematically, these can be defined by the eq. 7, 8, 9 and 10.

328

$$329 \text{2 day comp.strength} \geq \text{User defined 2 – day comp.strength} \quad (7)$$

$$330 \text{28 day comp.strength} \geq \text{User defined 28 – day comp.strength} \quad (8)$$

$$331 \text{Cost} \leq \text{User defined cost} \quad (9)$$

$$332 \text{CO}_2 \text{ equivalent} \leq \text{User defined CO}_2 \text{ equivalent} \quad (10)$$

333

334 It is to be noted that since compressive strength is usually targeted as high as possible
335 and cost and carbon footprint are targeted as low as possible, the user-defined
336 compressive strength has been defined as the lower bound for compressive strength
337 while the user-defined cost and CO₂ equivalent values have been defined as higher
338 bounds.

339

340 Finally, the objective function was maximized taking into account all the constraints using
341 the academic version of the Gurobi solver in Python, which typically employs simplex
342 method for solving linear programs.

343

344 *2.5 Case studies and experimental validation*

345

346 *2.5.1 Case studies*

347

348 Two primary cases were analyzed, focusing on CEM 42.5N and 32.5N strength classes, with
349 specific constraints on cost and CO₂ equivalent emissions. Each case generated four distinct
350 solutions corresponding to the different combinations of categorical variables. The
351 framework maintains flexibility in constraints and importance factors, provided the combined
352 constraints and variable bounds define a valid design space. The two cases have been
353 described below:

354

355 *Case 1: 42.5N strength class*

356

357 Table 3 summarizes the requirements of the user as explained in section 2.4.2. In this case, it
358 was assumed that the 28-compressive strength is more important (60 %) than cost (30 %)
359 and CO₂ equivalent- (10 %). 28-day compressive strength was assigned the highest
360 weightage in terms of optimization importance since it is a data-driven model with parameter
361 uncertainties.

362

363
364
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Table 3: Case 2 requirements

Property	User requirements
2-day compressive strength	≥ 20 MPa
28-day compressive strength	≥ 42.5 MPa (Importance 60 %)
Cost	≤ 110 euros/ton (Importance 30 %)
CO ₂ equivalent	≤ 550 kgCO ₂ /ton (Importance 10 %)
Water-to-binder ratio	≥ 0.475

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An additional criteria of water-to-binder ratio greater than or equal to 0.475 has also been added based on laboratory experience where the target flow diameter was 180 – 200 mm

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Case 2: 32.5N strength class

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373
374

Table 4 summarizes the requirements of the user in terms of constraints as explained in section 2.4.2. The importance factors are identical to that of case 1.

375
376

Table 4: Case 2 requirements

Property	User requirements
2-day compressive strength	≥ 10 MPa
28-day compressive strength	≥ 32.5 MPa (Importance 60 %)
Cost	≤ 100 euros/ton (Importance 30 %)
CO ₂ equivalent	≤ 500 kg CO ₂ /ton (Importance 10 %)
Water-to-binder ratio	≥ 0.475

377
378
379
380

Similar to case 1, an additional criteria of water-to-binder ratio greater than or equal to 0.475 has also been added to reach a target flow of 180 – 200 mm.

381
382

2.5.2 Experimental validation

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Based on the 8 mix designs (4 for each case) generated by the Python code, 4 mix designs (2 for each case) were considered for making mortar specimens in the laboratory for validation and 2-day, 7-day and 28-day compressive strength were measured. The results were then compared to the predicted compressive strength at these ages from the mix designs generated by the MOLP method.

388
389

3. Results and discussions

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3.1 Characterization of materials

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3.1.1 Chemical and mineralogical characterization

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The data obtained from XRF tests has been summarized in Table 5 while Fig. 2 shows the XRD plot for the copper slag used in this paper. The copper slag in this paper is characterized by >50 % FeO (high iron content), 87 % amorphous content with the presence of fayalite and magnetite phases.

399

Table 5: Chemical composition of the raw materials used* in wt %

Oxide	FeO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Others
Copper slag	52	32	4	3	2	7
Portland cement	4	18	5	63	1	9
Limestone	<1	<1	<1	99	<1	<1

400
401
402
403

*Composition of other oxides and LOI have been included in the 'Others' column

404
405
406
407
408

Fig. 2: XRD plot of the copper slag from Aurubis (M: Magnetite, F: Fayalite)

3.1.2 Physical characterization

409 The physical parameter measurements have been summarized in Table 6. As expected for the
410 slag with the higher fineness, the d₁₀, d₅₀ and d₉₀ values are higher.

411

Table 6: Physical properties of copper slag

Property	Copper slag with higher fineness	Copper slag with lower fineness
Blaine fineness (Specific Surface Area) [cm ² /g]	4400	2700
d ₁₀ [μm]	0.8	3.5
d ₅₀ [μm]	6.9	28.8
d ₉₀ [μm]	27.1	82.9

412

3.2 Regression analysis for experimentally designed data

414 This section provides an overview of the performance of the regression models, visualization
415 and quality checks.

3.2.1 Overview of the regression models

417 Table 7 shows the estimates and p-values of the regression models for normalized 2-day, 7-
418 day and 28-day compressive strength variables.

419

420

Table 7: Estimates and p-values of the linear regression models for compressive strength

Parameter	Estimate for 2-day strength	p-values for 2-day strength	Estimate for 7-day strength	p-values for 7-day strength	Estimate for 28-day strength	p-values for 28-day strength
Intercept	2.71	0.000	2.64	0.000	2.40	0.000
Copper slag (wt %)	-0.02	0.000	-0.02	0.000	-0.02	0.000
Limestone (wt %)	-0.02	0.000	-0.03	0.000	-0.03	0.000
Water-to-binder ratio	-2.55	0.001	-2.21	0.000	-1.85	0.110
Copper slag fineness [4400]	0.01	0.819	0.01	0.721	0.11	0.041
Cement type [R]	0.10	0.002	0.05	0.060	0.10	0.054

421

422 The regression analysis presented in Table 7 demonstrates that copper slag content and
 423 limestone content are the primary influential factors across all models. The water-to-binder
 424 ratio shows statistical significance for compressive strength measurements at 2 and 7 days but
 425 not at 28 days. While a comprehensive technical explanation for this phenomenon remains to
 426 be established, it may be attributed to complex parameter interactions not currently
 427 incorporated in the simplified models. Regarding slag fineness, the analysis reveals no
 428 statistical significance in compressive strength at 2 and 7 days; however, it emerges as a
 429 significant factor at 28 days. This delayed influence can be attributed to the latent reactivity
 430 characteristics of copper slag, where finer particles facilitate enhanced reactivity at later ages.
 431 These findings align with the research by (Hallet et al. 2022), who observed increased
 432 reactivity of copper slags beyond 7 days. Furthermore, the finer particle size distribution of
 433 CEM I 52.5R compared to CEM I 52.5N results in a more pronounced effect on 2-day
 434 compressive strength relative to 7- and 28-day measurements. This observation is primarily
 435 explained by Portland cement being the earliest reactive component in the copper slag-
 436 limestone-cement system, making the impact of cement fineness most evident during early-
 437 age strength development.

438

3.2.2 Regression visualization

439

Fig. 3 shows the scatter plots (compared to the 45° ideal prediction line) for training and
 440 testing data sets for 2-day, 7-day and 28-day compressive strength.

441

442

(a)

(b)

443

444

(c)

(d)

445

446

(e)

(f)

447 **Fig. 3:** (a) Predicted vs original data for 2-day normalized training compressive strength; (b)
 448 Predicted vs original for 2-day normalized testing compressive strength; (c) Predicted vs
 449 original data for 7-day normalized training compressive strength; (d) Predicted vs original for
 450 7-day normalized testing compressive strength; (e) Predicted vs original data for 28-day
 451 normalized training compressive strength; (f) Predicted vs original for 28-day normalized
 452 testing compressive strength

453 From Fig 3, it can be visually observed that the scatter along the 45° ideal prediction line is
 454 maximum for 28-day compressive strength. Hence, it points to the fact that the predictive
 455 ability of the linear regression model is worst in the case of 28-day compressive strength
 456 among other ages. It is possible that the copper slag shows latent reactivity at 28 days,
 457 affecting the compressive strength and hence, inducing non-linearities in the model. Further
 458 assessments are necessary to comment on the performance of the linear regression models
 459 over time.

460 3.2.3 Model fitting quality check

461 While data visualization can quickly identify problems in data and model fitting through
 462 quick qualitative checks, quantitative checks are necessary based on R^2 , MAE and RMSE
 463 values on both training and testing data sets. Table 8 summarizes the model fitting checks
 464 conducted on training and testing data sets for 2-day, 7-day and 28-day compressive strength
 465 regression models.

466 **Table 8:** Model fit checks for compressive strength regression models

Response variable	Type of metric	Training data	Testing data
2-day compressive strength	MAE	0.065	0.045
	RMSE	0.080	0.065
	R^2	0.884	0.920
7-day compressive strength	MAE	0.051	0.070
	RMSE	0.066	0.088
	R^2	0.920	0.845
28-day compressive strength	MAE	0.109	0.080
	RMSE	0.132	0.112
	R^2	0.720	0.745

467

468 The regression models demonstrated consistent performance across both training and testing
 469 datasets, as evidenced by comparable MAE, RMSE, and R^2 values shown in Table 8. This
 470 consistency suggests robust model performance, though comprehensive validation required
 471 additional k-fold cross-validation analysis. When benchmarked against previous research
 472 (Chithra et al. 2016) examining copper slag as a fine aggregate, the models achieved superior
 473 performance metrics across R^2 , RMSE, and MAE values. This improvement indicates
 474 enhanced predictive capabilities compared to existing literature. The analysis revealed
 475 notable differences in predictive accuracy across the three temporal models (2-day, 7-day,
 476 and 28-day compressive strength). The 2-day and 7-day compressive strength models
 477 demonstrated superior predictive performance, characterized by lower MAE and RMSE
 478 values for both training and testing datasets. These models also achieved higher R^2 values,
 479 indicating better fit to the experimental data. The 28-day compressive strength model showed
 480 comparatively reduced accuracy, evidenced by:

- 481 • Higher MAE and RMSE values across both training and testing datasets
- 482 • Lower R^2 values compared to the early-stage models

483 These findings align with the data visualization results presented in section 3.2.2, confirming
 484 the superior predictive capability of the early-age models. Further analysis of specific case

485 studies and the corresponding variance between predicted and experimental results is detailed
486 in section 3.4.

487 In addition to the aforementioned metrics, k-fold cross validation was also conducted to
488 estimate the performance of the model over the entire data set. Mean Absolute Error (MAE)
489 was used to quantify the error over the different combinations of training and testing data sets
490 in the cross-validation problem. Table 9 shows the results from the k-fold cross validation
491 tests over 5 different splits of the dataset. In this problem, k has been considered to be 5.

492 **Table 9:** MAE results from 5-fold cross validation

Data splits	2-day compressive strength	7-day compressive strength	28-day compressive strength
Split 1	0.075	0.070	0.100
Split 2	0.041	0.063	0.147
Split 3	0.065	0.059	0.127
Split 4	0.071	0.038	0.081
Split 5	0.079	0.074	0.142
Average	0.066	0.061	0.119

493

494 As mentioned earlier in this section, the error in prediction was the highest for 28-day
495 compressive strength, which is corroborated by the cross-validation results here. From Table
496 9, it is also interesting to look at the individual MAE values over the entire dataset for each
497 split. Ideally, the MAE values should be as close to each other as possible for different splits
498 of a dataset which indicates homogeneity over the dataset. However, in this problem, there is
499 a maximum deviation of 37.9% from the mean MAE for 2-day compressive strength, 37.7%
500 from the mean MAE for 7-day compressive strength and 31.9% from the mean MAE for 28-
501 day compressive strength. These values can be minimized by collecting more data points in
502 the domain of study. In this problem, 5-fold cross-validation was just used to check the
503 performance of the model over the entire dataset.

504 *3.3 MOLP method*

505 In this section, two different case studies pertaining to cement strength classes of 42.5N and
506 32.5N have been solved using the framework described in this paper involving experimental
507 design, machine learning and multi-objective optimization.

508 *3.3.1 Case 1 (42.5N strength class)*

509 Table 10 shows the mix design obtained from the algorithm developed as a part of this paper.

510

511

Table 10: Optimal mix designs based on the optimization algorithm for case 2

Slag fineness and cement type	Mix component	Amount
2700 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5N	Copper slag (wt % of total binder)	20.0
	Limestone (wt % of total binder)	14.8
	Portland cement (wt % of total binder)	65.2
	Water-to-binder ratio	0.475
4400 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5R	Copper slag (wt % of total binder)	20.0
	Limestone (wt % of total binder)	20.7
	Portland cement (wt % of total binder)	59.3
	Water-to-binder ratio	0.475
4400 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5N	Copper slag (wt % of total binder)	20.0
	Limestone (wt % of total binder)	16.5
	Portland cement (wt % of total binder)	63.5
	Water-to-binder ratio	0.475
2700 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5R	Copper slag (wt % of total binder)	20.0
	Limestone (wt % of total binder)	19.1
	Portland cement (wt % of total binder)	60.9
	Water-to-binder ratio	0.475

512

513 Since 28-day compressive strength was assumed to be the response with the highest priority
514 in this specific case and also the value was constrained to be greater than or equal to 42.5
515 MPa, copper slag content for every mix was fixed at the lower bound of 20 wt% since
516 replacement of Portland cement with copper slag typically reduces compressive strength.
517 Table 11 shows the predicted values of the response variables and also experimental
518 validation of 2 mixes out of 4 for the compressive strength values. The other two mix design
519 property predictions are shown in Appendix C (Table C.1).

520 It can be seen that the predicted values and experimental values are closely related for the
521 mix designs with 4400 cm²/g (copper slag fineness) and CEM I 52.5 R (cement type) and
522 2700 cm²/g (copper slag fineness) and CEM I 52.5 R (cement type), with average deviations
523 of 8.5 %, 6.3 % and 5.4 % for 2-day, 7-day and 28-day compressive strength respectively. As
524 far as the flow diameters are concerned in case 2, they are close to flow diameters measured
525 for standard Portland cement mortars (EN 196-1, 2016). Summarizing case 1, it was observed
526 that using approximately 61 wt% Portland cement, 20 wt% copper slag and 19 wt%
527 limestone powder, a mortar mix corresponding to 42.5 N strength class was obtained.
528 Additionally, it was possible to reduce the equivalent CO₂ to 458 kg_{CO2}/ton of binder from
529 693 kg_{CO2}/ton (for Portland cement mortars). This is well within the 550 kg_{CO2}/ton
530 recommendation by Cembureau (Cembureau, 2020) but with a lower strength class. More
531 reactive (and novel) SCMs like vitrified bauxite residue (Giels et al. 2022) would be suitable
532 to reach 52.5N strength class with similar equivalent CO₂ values. Solving a similar problem
533 using grid search techniques, Bharadwaj et al. (2024) lowered the CO₂ equivalent of concrete
534 mix designs but using the concept of carbon cost.

535

Table 11: Algorithm predictions and experimental results for mix designs for case 1

Slag fineness and cement type	Response variable	Model prediction	Experimental results
4400 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5N	2-day compressive strength [MPa]	21.3	24.7 ± 0.77
	7-day compressive strength [MPa]	34.7	36.4 ± 1.03
	28-day compressive strength [MPa]	49.0	53.1 ± 0.12
	Cost [Euros/ton]	110.0	N/A
	CO ₂ equivalent [kgCO ₂ /ton]	458.0	N/A
	Flow diameter [mm]	N/A	193
	2700 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5R	2-day compressive strength [MPa]	22.2
7-day compressive strength [MPa]		34.0	36.6 ± 1.50
28-day compressive strength [MPa]		46.5	47.6 ± 0.51
Cost [Euros/ton]		110.0	N/A
CO ₂ equivalent [kgCO ₂ /ton]		515.8	N/A
Flow diameter [mm]		N/A	181.5

537

538 *3.3.2 Case 2 (32.5N strength class)*

539 Table 12 shows the mix design obtained from the algorithm developed as a part of this paper.

540 **Table 12:** Optimal mix designs based on optimization algorithm for case 2

Slag fineness and cement type	Mix component	Amount
2700 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5N	Copper slag (wt % of total binder)	20.0
	Limestone (wt % of total binder)	24.9
	Portland cement (wt % of total binder)	55.1
	Water-to-binder ratio	0.475
4400 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5R	Copper slag (wt % of total binder)	22.5
	Limestone (wt % of total binder)	28.4
	Portland cement (wt % of total binder)	49.1
	Water-to-binder ratio	0.475
4400 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5N	Copper slag (wt % of total binder)	20.0
	Limestone (wt % of total binder)	26.6
	Portland cement (wt % of total binder)	53.4
	Water-to-binder ratio	0.475
2700 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5R	Copper slag (wt % of total binder)	20.1
	Limestone (wt % of total binder)	28.4
	Portland cement (wt % of total binder)	51.5
	Water-to-binder ratio	0.475

541 Since the requirements of compressive strength are less stringent than case 1, the copper slag
 542 content is not strictly bound to be 20 wt%, whereas two of the four solutions have a copper
 543 slag content greater than 20 wt%. Table 13 shows the predicted values of the response
 544 variables and experimental validation of 2 mixes out of 4 for the compressive strength values.
 545 Predictions for the rest of the two mixes are reported in Appendix C, Table C.2.

546 **Table 13:** Algorithm predictions and experimental results for mix designs for case 3

Slag fineness and cement type	Response variable	Model prediction	Experimental results
2700 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5N	2-day compressive strength [MPa]	16.6	18.1 ± 0.69
	7-day compressive strength [MPa]	27.9	29.0 ± 1.87
	28-day compressive strength [MPa]	37.6	41.0 ± 1.13
	Cost [Euros/ton]	100.0	N/A
	CO ₂ equivalent [kgCO ₂ /ton]	401.3	N/A
	Flow diameter [mm]	N/A	185
	4400 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5N	2-day compressive strength [MPa]	15.8
7-day compressive strength [MPa]		26.8	26.0 ± 2.27
28-day compressive strength [MPa]		39.8	38.9 ± 4.27
Cost [Euros/ton]		100.0	N/A
CO ₂ equivalent [kgCO ₂ /ton]		390.1	N/A
Flow diameter [mm]		N/A	193.5

547
 548 Similar to case 1, the predicted values and experimental values are closely related for the mix
 549 designs with 2700 cm²/g (copper slag fineness) and CEM I 52.5 N (cement type) and 4400
 550 cm²/g (copper slag fineness) and CEM I 52.5 N (cement type), with average deviations of 9.6
 551 %, 3.5 % and 5.7 % for 2-day, 7-day and 28-day compressive strength respectively. As far as
 552 the flow diameters are concerned in case 2, they are close to flow diameters measured for
 553 standard Portland cement mortars (EN 196-1, 2016). Summarizing case 2, it was observed
 554 that using approximately 49 wt% Portland cement, 23 wt% copper slag and 28 wt%
 555 limestone powder, a mortar mix corresponding to CEM I 32.5 N strength class was obtained.
 556 Also, similar to case 1, the equivalent CO₂ values are well within the limits suggested by
 557 Cembureau (Cembureau, 2020) but with two strength classes lower than 52.5N.

558

559 4. Conclusions

560 This paper presented a framework for creating blended cements with copper slags, limestone
 561 and Portland cement. The framework was built based on fundamentals of experimental
 562 design, statistics, machine learning and mathematical optimization. While this paper deals
 563 with a case study on ternary blended cement systems, it is possible to apply this problem to
 564 any kind of concrete mix designs with various starting raw materials. The framework was

565 also tested to generate mix designs pertaining to 42.5N and 32.5N strength classes with low
566 cost and CO₂ equivalent. The key takeaways from this study are summarized below:

- 567 • A reduction in Portland cement content by up to 51% was possible based on different
568 levels of strength requirement. Specifically, a reduction of up to 40% was possible in
569 order to achieve the strength class of 42.5N and up to 51% in order to achieve the
570 strength requirements of the 32.5N strength class.
- 571 • Using the copper slag-limestone-Portland cement system, it was possible to reach a
572 strength class of 42.5N with CO₂ equivalent values lower than 550 kg_{CO2}/ton,
573 specified by Cembureau (Cembureau, 2020).
- 574 • The combination of DSD, augmented DSD and FFFD resulted in a near-uniform
575 distribution of points in the design space, which helped in training the regression
576 models used in the problem. In case of no material constraints, larger number of data
577 points would result in better prediction accuracy and model performance.
- 578 • Linear regression models were typically enough to fit the data generated in this study.
579 Linear regression models for 28-day compressive strength showed a higher degree of
580 error for both training and testing data than those for 2-day and 7-day compressive
581 strength models. While this needs further investigation, it is possible that late-age
582 reactions of copper slags in the blended cement system induced non-linearity in the
583 compressive strength equation.
- 584 • Multi-objective linear program (MOLP) served as an effective solution for this
585 problem where linear models approximated compressive strength reasonably well. It
586 was also possible to assign importance factors to the different response variables
587 depending on user requirements. For the MOLP algorithm, however, confidence
588 intervals for the regression models were not considered for the problem. In future
589 works, the authors plan to add a framework based on parameter uncertainty
590 quantifications where the effects of confidence intervals on the optimization results
591 would be investigated.

592
593 A first version of the framework developed in this paper is already available as an online
594 application as a part of SREWay: database designed for the metallurgical, cement and
595 concrete industry/academia (<https://sreway.info/>). This tool is expected to assist industries
596 like aluminum and copper where it will be possible to quantify the valorization potential of
597 their residues/slugs and also the cement and concrete industries who can efficiently test the
598 potential of new SCMs and building material precursors based on a framework supported by
599 ML and optimization algorithms.

600

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606

607 **Declaration**

608 During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Claude.ai in order to polish the already
609 written text for better textual flow. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and
610 edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published
611 article.

612

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836 **Appendix A**

837 Table A.1 shows the mix designs used for training and testing the regression models in this
 838 paper while Table A.2 shows their corresponding flow diameter, 2-day, 7-day and 28-day
 839 compressive strength values along with standard deviations.

840 **Table A.1:** Mix designs generated from DSD and space filling designs

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Mix no.	Copper slag (wt%)	Cement (wt %)	Limestone (wt %)	Water/Binder	Fineness (cm ² /g)	Cement type
1	20	59.3	20.7	0.45	2700	R
2	30	60.9	9.1	0.45	2700	N
3	20	69.6	10.4	0.5	4400	N
4	20	51.6	28.4	0.475	2700	N
5	40	44.4	15.6	0.5	4400	N
6	40	38.7	21.3	0.5	2700	R
7	30	51.9	18.1	0.475	2700	N
8	20	69.6	10.4	0.5	2700	R
9	20	51.6	28.4	0.45	4400	R
10	40	38.7	21.3	0.45	4400	N
11	40	52.2	7.8	0.45	4400	R
12	40	52.2	7.8	0.475	4400	R
13	40	38.7	21.3	0.45	2700	R
14	40	52.2	7.8	0.5	2700	N
15	30	51.9	18.1	0.475	4400	R
16	30	45.2	24.8	0.5	4400	R
17	20	69.6	10.4	0.45	4400	N
18	20	51.6	28.4	0.5	2700	N
19	40	52.2	7.8	0.45	4400	N
20	40	38.7	21.3	0.45	2700	N
21	40	38.7	21.3	0.5	4400	N
22	20	51.6	28.4	0.45	4400	N
23	40	52.2	7.8	0.5	2700	R
24	20	69.6	10.4	0.5	2700	N
25	20	69.6	10.4	0.45	2700	R
26	20	51.6	28.4	0.5	4400	R
27	20.2	51.5	28.3	0.5	2700	N
28	34.9	42.3	22.8	0.48	4400	N
29	24.6	49.6	25.8	0.49	2700	R
30	21.5	53.8	24.7	0.49	4400	R
31	21.1	61.1	17.7	0.47	2700	R
32	28.0	55.4	16.6	0.5	4400	R
33	20.6	69.1	10.4	0.49	4400	N
34	23.3	55.2	21.5	0.48	2700	N
35	32.9	50.8	16.3	0.49	2700	N
36	39.6	42.6	17.9	0.49	4400	R
37	36.7	41.9	21.4	0.5	4400	N
38	31.4	50.1	18.5	0.5	2700	R
39	39.8	52.4	7.9	0.46	2700	N
40	38.5	52.5	8.9	0.5	4400	N

41	37.6	49.1	13.3	0.48	2700	R
42	35.7	54.1	10.3	0.49	4400	R
43	34.2	52.6	13.2	0.45	2700	N
44	30.5	59.9	9.6	0.45	2700	R
45	32.1	55.7	12.2	0.47	4400	N
46	20.1	66.6	13.3	0.45	4400	R
47	26.4	48.1	25.5	0.45	2700	N
48	28.9	49.0	22.1	0.46	4400	N
49	33.1	44.6	22.3	0.46	2700	R
50	24.3	56.9	18.8	0.46	4400	R
51	38.7	44.4	16.9	0.45	4400	N

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Table A.2: Flow diameter, 2-day, 7-day and 28-day compressive strength along with standard deviations

Mix no.	Flow diameter (mm)	Std. dev. Of flow (mm)	2-day comp. strength (MPa)	Std. dev. Of 2-day strength (MPa)	7-day comp. strength (MPa)	Std. dev. Of 7-day comp. strength (MPa)	28-day comp. strength (MPa)	Std. dev. of 28-day comp. strength
1	153	1.41	23.4	1.62	36.7	2.73	48.8	1.78
2	161	4.24	21.8	0.23	32.5	1.07	45.1	4.03
3	191	2.83	26.7	2.84	40.4	2.80	56.1	0.13
4	172	1.41	17.2	1.33	24.1	0.75	34.8	1.83
5	187.5	0.71	10.2	0.34	20.9	1.06	38.9	3.77
6	189.5	2.12	9.8	0.47	15.2	1.04	25.1	0.72
7	181.5	0.71	15.5	1.86	24.6	0.71	35.8	0.33
8	187.5	0.71	25.6	0.87	37.2	0.65	52.6	0.07
9	N/A	N/A	15.4	0.06	24.9	1.51	39.0	4.03
10	157.5	3.54	6.9	1.26	13.2	0.60	21.9	1.85
11	155	2.83	19.8	2.38	30.7	0.06	48.9	2.81
12	181	1.41	17.8	0.03	34.3	3.18	50.4	0.98
13	155.5	0.71	14.2	0.41	22.1	0.44	35.4	0.46
14	196	4.24	14.6	0.19	23.7	0.58	27.6	1.23
15	164.5	2.12	17.4	1.78	29.9	2.47	42.0	4.31
16	192.5	0.71	12.5	0.08	20.7	0.45	35.9	2.45
17	165	1.41	27.2	0.80	40.1	0.11	47.8	0.72
18	191.5	0.71	13.7	1.39	24.2	0.41	32.4	1.36
19	156	1.41	14.6	0.39	28.9	1.53	43.0	1.68
20	163.5	0.71	9.3	0.65	17.2	1.04	25.4	0.09
21	196	2.83	6.3	0.30	14.1	1.24	23.1	1.36
22	156.5	0.71	16.3	0.13	28.0	0.84	39.4	1.23
23	198.5	0.71	12.6	0.59	21.1	1.35	30.6	2.51
24	193	1.41	21.8	0.81	36.4	2.20	48.1	3.15
25	163.5	7.78	29.6	0.08	44.3	0.70	52.7	3.94
26	190	2.83	13.9	0.37	24.5	0.22	33.4	1.54
27	205	4.24	11.7	0.36	25.5	0.10	35.7	0.38
28	196.5	6.36	11.0	0.15	20.3	0.00	37.1	0.40
29	182.5	2.12	15.8	0.35	24.6	0.29	37.9	0.61

30	185.5	0.71	19.5	0.60	28.8	0.52	48.2	0.63
31	177	1.41	22.9	0.08	34.6	0.61	49.4	0.18
32	189	0	18.0	0.30	27.4	0.54	46.9	2.89
33	N/A	N/A	23.8	0.32	42.4	0.02	53.6	4.57
34	197	4.24	13.3	0.33	25.9	0.28	38.4	1.57
35	197.5	2.12	11.5	0.09	25.2	0.06	40.1	0.61
36	191	4.24	11.5	0.49	19.7	1.01	35.0	2.38
37	205	12.73	10.0	0.78	17.9	1.42	33.0	0.81
38	204.5	3.54	15.2	0.30	25.2	0.52	39.2	0.28
39	188	2.83	12.8	0.47	27.4	0.20	43.7	0.63
40	212.5	9.19	15.9	0.01	26.7	0.55	46.9	0.20
41	194	4.24	15.2	0.90	24.9	1.16	39.9	1.87
42	199	1.41	18.2	0.35	30.0	2.14	49.8	1.27
43	179.5	2.12	20.2	0.73	31.9	1.25	49.3	2.83
44	172	0	25.1	0.16	37.2	2.05	55.3	1.21
45	196	0	16.9	0.47	27.7	2.05	47.8	0.67
46	166	7.07	27.9	1.74	39.1	1.06	57.2	0.98
47	178.5	0.71	17.2	0.36	27.1	2.04	40.3	1.09
48	175.5	0.71	16.4	1.01	28.1	1.28	43.7	0.75
49	201.5	10.61	10.3	0.35	17.9	1.10	29.1	1.70
50	164	7.07	21.8	0.99	33.4	1.31	50.7	0.87
51	175	0.00	13.3	0.55	22.1	0.05	37.2	2.28

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849 **Appendix B**

850 Appendix B highlights details about the CO₂ equivalent calculations used in this paper. Table
 851 B.1 shows a summary of the calculations from the EcoInvent database. The following
 852 assumptions were considered for this paper:

- 853 • Since it was not possible to measure the energy equivalent during grinding, the CO₂
 854 equivalent of copper slag was based under the assumption that the Bond Work Index
 855 (BWI) of copper slag used in this study is 19 kWh/ton¹.
- 856 • The CO₂ equivalent of CEM I 52.5N OPC was assumed to be 693 kg_{CO2}/ton² and the
 857 CO₂ equivalent of CEM I 52.5R OPC is 817 kg_{CO2}/ton³.
- 858 • The freight distances were measured using Google Earth which can differ based on
 859 the mode of transport used for transferring the materials.

860 **Table B.1:** CO₂ equivalent details of the materials used in this paper

Input	Parameter	Comment	Reference
Limestone	Processing	Quarrying, crushing and grinding	Assumption
Limestone	Supplier	Carmeuse plant	
Limestone	Distance	64 km by truck	Estimated using Google Earth
Limestone	Electricity	Belgium	
Limestone	Total CO₂ eq. kg/t	21	Calculated using the software "LCA for Experts" (former GaBi)
Copper slag	Processing	Grinding	Assumption (22 kWh/t)
Copper slag	Supplier	Aurubis AG (Hauptverwaltung), Hovestraße 50, 20539 Hamburg, Germany	
Copper slag	Distance	726 km by ship (5000 mt) and 66 km by truck	Estimated using Google Earth
Copper slag	Electricity	Belgium	
Copper slag	Total CO₂ eq. kg/t	70	Calculated using the software "LCA for Experts" (former GaBi)
Copper slag	Processing	Extra grinding	Assumption (42 kWh/t)
Copper slag	Supplier	Aurubis AG (Hauptverwaltung), Hovestraße 50, 20539 Hamburg, Germany	
Copper slag	Distance	726 km by ship (5000 mt) and 66 km by truck	Estimated using Google Earth
Copper slag	Electricity	Belgium	
Copper slag	Total CO₂ eq. kg/t	73	Calculated using the software "LCA for Experts" (former GaBi)

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878 **Appendix C**

879 Appendix C shows the additional predicted optimal designs which has not been validated in
 880 the laboratory and hence not included in the main body of the paper.

881 **Table C.1:** Algorithm predictions for mix designs for case 1

Slag fineness and cement type	Response variable	Model prediction
2700 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5N	2-day compressive strength [MPa]	22.1
	7-day compressive strength [MPa]	35.8
	28-day compressive strength [MPa]	46.8
	Cost [Euros/ton]	110.0
	CO ₂ equivalent [kg _{CO2} /ton]	469.2
4400 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5R	2-day compressive strength [MPa]	21.4
	7-day compressive strength [MPa]	33.0
	28-day compressive strength [MPa]	48.8
	Cost [Euros/ton]	110.0
	CO ₂ equivalent [kg _{CO2} /ton]	503.3

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883 **Table C.2:** Algorithm predictions and experimental results for mix designs for case 2

Slag fineness and cement type	Response variable	Model prediction
4400 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5R	2-day compressive strength [MPa]	15.9
	7-day compressive strength [MPa]	25.1
	28-day compressive strength [MPa]	39.9
	Cost [Euros/ton]	100.0
	CO ₂ equivalent [kg _{CO2} /ton]	423.8
2700 cm ² /g and CEM I 52.5R	2-day compressive strength [MPa]	17.0
	7-day compressive strength [MPa]	26.6
	28-day compressive strength [MPa]	37.8
	Cost [Euros/ton]	100.0
	CO ₂ equivalent [kg _{CO2} /ton]	440.5

Preprint not peer reviewed

Graphical abstract

Fig. 1: PCA visualization of the experimental design

Fig. 2: XRD plot of the copper slag from Aurubis (M: Magnetite, F: Fayalite)

a)

b)

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Fig. 3: (a) Predicted vs original data for 2-day normalized training compressive strength; (b) Predicted vs original for 2-day normalized testing compressive strength; (c) Predicted vs original data for 7-day normalized training compressive strength; (d) Predicted vs original for 7-day normalized testing compressive strength; (e) Predicted vs original data for 28-day normalized training compressive strength; (f) Predicted vs original for 28-day normalized testing compressive strength